

GREEN SCENT

SMART CITIZEN EDUCATION
FOR A GREEN FUTURE

Project start date: 01/01/2022 | Duration: 36 months

D1.5 - GreenSCENT Competence Framework User Guide

Due date of the Deliverable: 31-10-2024

Actual submission date: 20-11-2024

Project	GreenSCENT – Smart Citizen Education for a Green Future
Call ID	H2020-LC-GD-2020-3-2020
Work Package	WP1 – GreenSCENT Competence Framework
Work Package Leader	UNINETTUNO
Deliverable Leader	UNSPMF
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Deliverable Nature	<i>Report</i>
Dissemination level	<i>Public</i>
Version	1.0
Revision	Final

1. Document Info

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1.4. Document History

Version #	Author/s	Date	Changes
0.1	Biljana Basarin	01/10/24	Table of Contents and first draft
0.2	Biljana Basarin, Miroslav Vujcic, Gian Andrea Giacobone, Ugljesa Stankov	25/10/24	Complete draft ready for revision
0.3	Biljana Basarin, Miroslav Vujcic	30/10/24	Document updated with the contributions received from Alessandro Pollini (peer review)
0.4	Biljana Basarin, Miroslav Vujcic	30/10/24	Document updated with the contributions received from Jelena Desnica (peer review)
1.0	Biljana Basarin	31/10/24	Final Release

1.5. Document Data

Keywords	<i>Learning design, Competence Framework, User Guide</i>
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Peer Review date	25-10-2024
Submission date	20-11-2024

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1. Introduction

This document presents the content related to the deliverable D1.5 GreenSCENT Competence Framework Use Guide. It reports the practical how-to implementation guide to help educators, teachers, professors, educational institutions, HR managers, employers, and other interested stakeholders implement the GreenSCENT Competence Framework. The guide supports academic, open innovation, and awareness-raising contexts to help citizens and younger learners develop literacy and pro-environmental competencies around the eight macro topics of the Green Deal.

The deliverable acts as a practical user guide that documents every step of the educational framework developed by GreenSCENT to autonomously set up and conduct the GreenSCENT learning experiences in sustainability education in different academic and professional contexts and communities at various levels of sustainable literacy.

The deliverable documents the general structure and the step-by-step instructions of the instructional design methodology and related tools and templates necessary to conduct the GreenSCENT learning scenario in sustainability education.

The document is divided into three main sections that will describe:

1. The objectives of the GreenSCENT Competence Framework User Guide;
2. The step-by-step implementation process;
3. The evaluation methodology is linked to the European Certification for Climate and Environmental Literacy (ECCEL).

2. User Guide: the GreenSCENT Framework

2.1. GreenSCENT and GreenComp – what can the former tell us about the latter

The GreenSCENT framework (i.e. GreenSCENT Comp) has clear ties to GreenComp. The project was financed under the H2020-EU 3.5 programme SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Climate action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials [<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101036480>], under the topic Enabling citizens to act on climate change, for sustainable development and environmental protection through education, citizen science, observation initiatives, and civic engagement, which focuses on the creation of competence framework on the Green Deal themes. The principles and values impinging GreenScent are the same as those underpinning the GreenComp framework.

The GreenSCENT project began at the same time as the publication of the GreenComp framework, making it one of the first projects to incorporate GreenComp. As part of this, GreenSCENT developed a correspondence matrix linking the GreenComp framework to its objectives. The main contribution of GreenSCENT was to associate the eight areas of the Green Deal with GreenComp, developing skills and attitudes specifically addressed to pupils and teachers from secondary schools.

The case studies offer nuanced perspectives on the application and hurdles associated with the GreenComp framework across various dimensions:

- It exemplifies how GreenComp is embraced by other initiatives, serving as a conceptual tool to bridge related yet distinct competence frameworks.
- Given GreenComp and GreenSCENT's overlapping objectives and shared educational focus on competencies, GreenSCENT's challenges can provide valuable insights into the potential complexities facing GreenComp.

This section is organised as follows:

- Paragraph 2.2 explains the matching between GreenComp and the GreenScent Competence framework.
- Paragraph 2.3 provides examples of educational activities developed within GreenSCENT and highlights how they correspond to GreenComp, pointing out potential future research activities on its impact.
- Paragraph 2.4 highlights the challenges faced by GreenSCENT and argues that they are transferable to GreenComp.
- Paragraph 1.5 concludes with some recommendations.

2.2 The use of GreenComp for GreenSCENT – mapping a conceptual framework into practical activities

As explained below, the GreenSCENT Competence Framework integrates the eight Green Deal thematic areas and the GreenComp framework in a correspondence matrix of three pillars. Members of the GreenSCENT consortium had been (even before the formal start of the project itself) involved in the consultations related to the GreenComp framework. This has allowed a cross-fertilisation of ideas between GreenSCENT (and its predecessors) and GreenComp.

To understand how the three elements are matched, it is essential to notice that GreenSCENT is articulated in Competence Areas and Individual Competencies within each Area. For each of the eight Green Deal themes, a set of GreenSCENT Competence Areas (ranging from three to seven) is identified. In turn, each of these branches out into individual competencies. The matching with GreenComp occurs at the level of individual competence; hence, the network of interrelations is complex.

The tables below exemplify such matching. It indicates how the Green Deal areas are first articulated in broad GreenSCENT Competence Areas.

Table 1: Green Deal Areas and the corresponding competencies areas as outlined by GreenSCENT

Green Deal area	GreenSCENT competences areas
Biodiversity	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Biologically diverse ecosystem values 2. Embracing experimental learning 3. Ecosystems literacy 4. Psychological aspects for behavioural change 5. Nature restoration goals 6. Enabling transformative change
Circular Economy	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Understanding 2. Stakeholder engagement 3. Challenges 4. Communication 5. Circular Design and Technology
Clean Energy	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Understanding the Challenge 2. Embodying Clean Energy 3. Industry, Employment, Finance
Climate Change	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Climate Science and Practice Literacy 2. Climate Change Adaptation Leadership 3. Interdisciplinary communication boosting 4. Understanding the Challenge 5. Climate adaptation reaction 6. Smart and fast adaptation 7. Systemics adaptation economy and society
From farm to Fork	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sustainable food production 2. Sustainable food processing and distribution 3. Sustainable food consumption 4. Food loss and waste prevention
Green Building	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Green building, general competences 2. Green building material and resources 3. Green building products and technologies 4. Green building, part in economy

Smart Mobility	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Embodying sustainability 2. Awareness 3. Take action
Zero Pollution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Understanding the Challenge (ZP) 2. Embodying Zero Pollution (ZP) 3. Industry, Employment, Finance (ZP)

The link between GreenSCENT and GreenComp is also mapped into a so-called “Knowledge Graph.” The mapping between GreenComp and GreenSCENT is a conceptual framework that enables reflection on using GreenComp for the case study. It should be stressed, however, that such reflection is not actively pursued within the GreenSCENT project.

2.3 Examples of educational initiatives and their main goal linked to the GreenComp competencies

2.3.1 CleanAir@school

CleanAir@School [<https://www.green-scent.eu/cleanairschool/>] is an initiative launched in May 2022 within the GreenSCENT project. Its main objectives are to “enhance students' understanding of air pollution” and to raise awareness among the participants over the air pollution issue, driving them to adopt more sustainable attitudes and habits, especially concerning mobility. Through specific sensors (called passive samplers) placed by the pupils, students from 12 elementary schools in Girona (ES) monitored air pollution in and near schools and their surrounding areas for four weeks. After this, more than 150 sensors spread across the city were collected for analysis in an accredited laboratory.

Thanks to the initiative, students could apply several GreenComp Competencies, including 1.1 Valuing sustainability by assessing air pollution in their school environment and 2.1 Systems thinking by looking at how it affects their quality of life in different ambiances.

2.3.2 Microplastics in the Ocean

In May 2023, one of the GreenScent activities included the involvement of around 30 students from a school in Cardedeu (ES) to observe, analyse and assess the impact of microplastics on Catalonia's beaches (<https://www.green-scent.eu/small-particles-big-problem-exploring-microplastics-in-catalonias-beaches/>). The analysis was done through sampling spots taken across various areas of the beach and by gathering small sand samples. Finally, the students separated the microplastics in the samples from the sand collected. On one hand, the sand was “cleaned” from the microplastics, thus making the beaches less polluted. On the other hand, the pupils reused the plastic separated from the samples to create sculptures afterwards.

Thanks to the initiative, students could apply two GreenComp Competencies, including 1.1 Valuing sustainability and 2.1 Systems thinking, by looking at the circular use of plastics in the seam.

2.3.3 Youth Assemblies

GreenScent has implemented Youth Assemblies [<https://www.green-scent.eu/youth-assemblies/>] to increase and put youth participation at the forefront. The Youth Assemblies (YDAs) comprised 56 young people (between 15 and 25 years old) divided into four assemblies. The timeline of the Youth Assemblies was spread across the project implementation from October 2022 to January 2024. Participants come from both EU and non-EU countries (seven in total: Denmark, Finland, Greece, Italy, Romania, Serbia, and Spain). Thanks to the Mural app, GreenSCENT project managers and partners from UniNettuno and BSC (Barcelona

Supercomputing Centre) arranged online workshops, allowing participants to co-develop “tools and processes [...] and generate ideas and suggestions for the design and implementation of these tools in educational settings. They applied the following GreenComp competence: 1.1 Valuing sustainability, 2.1 Systems thinking, 2.2 Critical thinking, 3.3 Exploratory thinking.

2.3.4 Open Innovation Challenges

Open innovation challenges [<https://www.green-scent.eu/open-innovation-challenges/>], launched by the French company Agorize (part of the GreenSCENT consortium), aim at creating pre-entrepreneurial ideas in the field of sustainable food production consumption and waste management. The initiative allows participants to express their creativity and innovative ideas (using GreenComp 3.1 Future literacy, 3.2 Adaptability and 3.3 Exploratory thinking) on how to re-think food production and how to prevent and better manage the consequent waste coming from it (thereby exercising GreenComp 2.1 Systems thinking, 2.2 Critical thinking and 2.3 Problem framing). The event eventually led to the presentation of ideas and offered a fruitful network opportunity for attendees to exchange practices, knowledge, and challenges ahead to tackle the current global issues (Green Comp 4.2 Collective action).

2.4 Enabling Conditions and Challenges to developing green competences

4.1 Barriers and Obstacles

The initiatives and tools developed within GreenSCENT are designed to transcend national or local boundaries, enabling application across a diverse array of countries and environments, including urban and rural settings. Indeed, The GreenSCENT website has a dedicated page for tools and resources the community can use. Examples include a toolkit for children's green storytelling, a YouTube channel with project outputs and educational resources. The repository of resources is still at a preliminary stage, which reflects that the project is still not completed. However, it is already clear to the interviewees that replicability and scalability will be challenging, given the common ground between GreenSCENT and GreenComp. The challenges identified below shed light on the hurdles GreenComp itself will face in its diffusion.

More specifically, inclusion, down-scalability, replicability and contextualisation are critical.

Inclusion: The GreenSCENT consortium includes four schools; three are private and considered “elite”. In other words, the experimentation of educational practices occurred in an economically and socially privileged environment, potentially positively oriented towards environmental issues. It was therefore necessary to construct and implement a research protocol for “external pilots” to reach out to less privileged environments. To this aim, a set of instructional co-design workshops with local teachers in rural Romania, as well as the suburbs of Rome (Italy) and Spain through the UAB and their Summer Schools activities for students risking university exclusion. The workshops focussed on the accessibility of the digital resources produced and on the attention to the involvement of vulnerable groups in project activities. External pilots were allowed to test tools and activities for new target students in scenarios with fewer financial resources than the educational institutions presented in the consortium. The limited time available, the lack of financial means, technological resources, limited digital coverage (especially in rural areas) and the limited background knowledge about sustainability and competence frameworks (both GreenSCENT and GreenComp) posed significant challenges to implementing the activities foreseen in the GreenSCENT. Secondary school teachers required adequate training (kits prepared and tailored for them), indicating that accommodating a competent approach to teaching in sustainability is far from easy.

Down-scalability: While the project envisaged the use of innovative pedagogies enabled by digital technologies, in some contexts, the implementation of the project revealed that resources (background knowledge, connection, device availability and especially lack of time available) are only sometimes available for these goals. To ensure the replication of educational activities in different socio-economic-cultural contexts, GreenSCENT developed initiatives across different scenarios (high-resources and low-resources) to scale the technological requirements to activities based on paper prototypes. An example of the former is the tool case of developing interactive documentaries GreenVerse. An example of the latter is the development of tools to study “micro-plastics”, which is almost entirely analogue (but has the constraint of proximity to the sea). Adjusting to high and low resource scenarios is also relevant to other activities implementing GreenComp.

A trade-off between readiness and contextualisation of tools: The balance between an easy-to-adopt/ready-to-use tool/activity and a contextualised/customised one is difficult to strike. The experience of GreenSCENT suggests that it takes time to transfer the knowledge implicit in the GreenSCENT approach quickly. Indeed, acquiring the ability to teach through a competence-based method (be it GreenSCENT or GreenComp) requires time and resources that are only sometimes available. For this reason, GreenSCENT is trying to provide a heterogeneous range of possible teaching activities, producing a series of materials complementary to the competence framework to make it as easy as possible to choose tools and scenarios proposed suited to the contexts and resources available.

2.5 Lessons learnt and recommendations

This case study has focused on the H2020 project GreenSCENT, intending to extract lessons related to the diffusion and challenges of the GreenComp framework.

The reasons to focus on GreenSCENT are twofold: on the one hand, GreenSCENT is based on the same pedagogical principles of GreenComp and established a Competence Framework; on the other, it explicitly embeds GreenComp in its approach, with a matrix that creates a clear correspondence between the competences in the GreenComp and in the GreenSCENT frameworks.

This allows us to infer insights into the challenges embedded in competence-based environmental education and to scan activities closely aligned to GreenComp. Whilst GreenSCENT, as a project, has yet to produce all its results (the project will end in 2024), there are valuable lessons that have already been learnt and that can be transferred to GreenComp. In particular, competence-based environmental education is complex to develop and apply. Challenges emerge when adopting competency-based approaches across different environments, depending on their digitalisation level, specific characteristics and socio-economic environment. Any tool/initiative needs to be adapted to the specificities of each educational environment, which is costly in terms of time and resources. Nevertheless, while competence-based environmental education presents challenges, its significance cannot be overstated. Adapting competitive approaches to different scenarios is imperative for fostering a sustainable future.

3. User Guide: how-to implementation guide process

3.1. Introduction to the Educator Guide Process

This guide provides general guidelines for integrating sustainability education into academic and professional courses, programs or environments. It enables academic or professional stakeholders to prepare specific education learning plans to help their learners acquire adequate literacy and pro-environmental competencies related to the eight macro areas of the Green Deal: Biodiversity, Circular Economy, Clean Energy, Climate Change, From farm to Fork, Green Building, Smart Mobility, Zero Pollution.

The user guide provides a step-by-step instructional design for creating sustainability-focused learning experiences that adopt methodologies, materials, tools, and technologies developed within the GreenSCENT project. In particular, the GreenSCENT toolkit aims to enable educators to design many formative and engaging educational experiences associated with specific technologies specifically designed to address learning challenges in sustainability education, such as:

- GreenSCENT Knowledge Graph
- GreenSCENT Environmental Monitoring App
- GreenSCENT Citizen Journalism
- GreenSCENT Air Quality App
- GreenSCENT CleanAir@School
- GreenVerse 360 Interactive Documentary

The document is a proper educator guide that involves analysing learning needs, developing instructional objectives, creating the program's architecture content and steps, and evaluating the effectiveness of the learning.

The educational framework is mainly divided into four macro areas that are identified:

- **Stage A - Strategy:** This phase focuses on identifying learning needs and objectives related to a specific learning domain based on one of the macro areas of the Green Deal.
- **Stage B - Planning:** This phase defines the competencies the learner is expected to acquire according to the learning objectives that characterise the selected domain.
- **Stage C - Execution:** This phase sets up the entire practical educational experience and its corresponding expected outcomes, which will be conducted with the learners' involvement.
- **Stage D - Evaluation:** This phase assesses the learners' learning performance by evaluating the learning outcomes developed during the educational activities proposed in the execution stage.

This guide will detail all the steps needed to structure and orchestrate a learning program based on sustainability education in the following sessions, starting from these four macro stages.

Each step/activity in the instructional design process is associated with using or adopting one or more specific educational materials from the GreenSCENT training kit, which include:

- Competence tools:
 - GreenSCENT Competence Framework
 - GreenSCENT Skill Cards
 - GreenSCENT Competence Questionnaire
- Templates
 - GreenSCENT Instructional Design Template
 - GreenSCENT Use Case Template
 - GreenSCENT 360° Paper-Based Template
 - GreenSCENT Learning Performance Assessment Template
- Educational experience examples:
 - GreenSCENT Instructional Design Library
 - GreenSCENT Use Case Library
- Technology User Manuals:
 - GreenSCENT Knowledge Graph

- GreenSCENT Environmental Monitoring App
- GreenSCENT Citizen Journalism
- GreenSCENT Air Quality App
- GreenSCENT CleanAir@School
- GreenVerse 360 Interactive Documentary

These materials will help educators implement learning programs and evaluate learning performance in their academic or professional environments.

A comprehensive representation of the overall instructional design framework is presented as follows:

LINK to the framework: https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVLRsQsw=?share_link_id=382070771296

3.2. Educational Framework step-by-step process

3.2.1. Stage A - Strategy

Stage A of the GreenSCENT educational framework consists of two steps that allow academic or professional educators to strategically set up a specific learning program based on sustainability education to fill a particular educational gap or problem in their educational environment, program or curriculum according to the target audience's learning needs.

This first stage requires educators to determine the learning domain within one of the eight macro areas of the Green Deal based on specific learning objectives and outcomes that will characterise the expected learning program identified during the learning needs analysis.

In this stage, adopting the GreenSCENT competence framework leads the decision-making process by providing educators with essential information for identifying the correct learning domain and helping them compare learners' needs and characteristics to specific learning objectives of the eight macro areas of the Green Deal.

Step A.1: Identify learning needs

Premise: This strategic activity must involve a group of internal decision-makers, stakeholders, and other educators who can contribute to helping the educational framework adhere perfectly to the necessities and goals of a particular academic or professional institution.

A.1.1: Identify the target audience's learning needs in sustainability education according to the learning gap of a determined academic or professional environment or curriculum. Support this gap analysis by exploring the GreenSCENT Knowledge Graph.

A.1.2: Write down the most critical educational challenges the gap analysis highlighted during the research activity.

A.1.3: Using the GreenSCENT Competence Framework, address each learning need in the eight areas of the Green Deal.

Tool: GreenSCENT Competence Framework

The screenshot shows a table titled '1.1.2.1 Climate Change - 1.1 Climate Change Scientific Literacy'. The table has three columns: 'KSA', 'EDF', and 'Keywords'. It lists various competencies and their descriptions, categorized into Knowledge and Skills.

KSA	EDF	Keywords	
Knowledge	1	Knows climate change issues and the main causes for climate change.	Energy, issues
	2	Knows that the greenhouse effect is growing every year and understands that this problem can be at least partially solved at society level (e.g. reducing the electricity consumption, preserving electrical appliances, saving water, etc.)	partial solution, reducing consumption
	3	Knows the greenhouse heating factors and can discuss the economic, political and other factors related to the climate change issue.	cause, solution, political environment
	4	Knows the statistics or can predict and describe how the EU or OECD countries are dealing with greenhouse and climate change effect.	statistics, green deal, international deals
	5	Writes the consequences of political reaction and address gaps in scientific and societal understanding of climate change.	reaction, understanding gaps
	6	Knows other socio-scientific challenges indirectly related to the environmental, such as health, food, as well as the limitations.	social, scientific challenges
Skills	1	Describes and discusses appropriate uses for climate models, as well as the limitations.	limitations
	2	Draws on climate science knowledge to analyse and interpret the impact of climate change on the built and natural environment, and on the economic, political, cultural, and social systems.	impact, political, cultural, social, systems
	3	Can describe the factors causing climate change.	factor for climate change
	4	Can also evaluate if the harm made to the environment is returnable and is able to discuss what an individual can do about it.	returnable, unreturnable harm, natural climate change
	5	Can estimate the greenhouse effect causing factors per capita (e.g. CO2 emission, methane gas emission).	gas emission, personal responsibility
	6	Is able to engage with science-related issues, and with the ideas of science, as a reflective citizen.	engagement, community awareness
	7	Is able to analyse the current political strategies and policies for climate change.	strategies
	6	Describes the complex interconnections between climate and other systems (environmental, health, social, economic, and political) and integrates facts into climate systems analysis.	complexity, interaction, different environments
	7	Accesses and uses climate information provided through regional climate service centres (e.g. Pacific Climate Impacts Consortium, Durban, etc.) and is able to interpret global and local climate change trends, impacts, challenges and concerns, and use this information to inform policies and practices.	trends, impact, challenges, concerns

LINK to the tool:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1yz3oKsv8sbJDEQCtmmJJxt dj_hWKu9SO/edit#heading=h.4i7ojhp

Technological tool: GreenSCENT Knowledge Graph

LINK to the tool: https://publish.obsidian.md/greenscent/_START+HERE_

Step A.2: Define the learning domain and objectives

A.2.1: Select the Green Deal area that best fits the learning needs identified in the previous step as a learning domain.

A.2.2: Define the learning objectives by selecting one to five competencies in the chosen domain whose EQF adequately matches the target audience's existing competencies.

Tool: GreenSCENT Competence Framework

GREEN SCENT
SMART CITIZEN EDUCATION FOR A GREEN FUTURE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101036480

1.1.2. Competence definition (KSA)

1.1.2.1 Climate Change – 1.1 Climate Change Scientific Literacy

KSA	EQF	Statements	Keywords
Knowledge	1	Knows climate change issues and the main causes for climate change.	Energy, issues
	2	Knows that the greenhouse effect is growing every year and understands that this problem can be at least partially solved at society level (e.g. reducing the electricity consumption, preserving electrical appliances, saving water, etc.)	partial solution, reducing consumption
	3	Knows the greenhouse causing factors and can discuss the economic, political and other factors related to the climate change issue.	cause, solution, political environment
	4	Knows the statistics or can predict and describe how the EU or OECD countries are dealing with greenhouse and climate change effect.	statistics, green deal, international deals
	5	Writes the consequences of political inaction and address gaps in scientific and societal understanding of climate change.	inaction, understanding gaps
	6	Knows other socio-scientific challenges indirectly related to the environmental, such as health, food, as well as the limitations.	social, scientific challenges
Skills	1	Describes and proposes appropriate uses for climate models, as well as the limitations.	limitations
	2	Draws on climate science knowledge to analyse and interpret the impact of climate change on the built and natural environment, and on the economic, political, cultural, and social systems.	impact, political, cultural, social, systems
	3	Can describe the factors causing climate change.	factor for climate change
	4	Can also evaluate if the harm made to the environment is returnable and is able to discuss what an individual can do about it.	returnable, unreturnable harm, natural climate change
	5	Can estimate the greenhouse effect causing factors per capita (e.g. CO2 emission, methane gas emission).	gas emission, personal responsibility
	6	Is able to engage with science-related issues, and with the ideas of science, as a reflective citizen.	engagement, community approach
Skills	6	Is able to analyse the current political strategies and policies for climate change.	strategies
	7	Identifies the complex interactions between climate and other systems (environmental, health, social, economic, and political) and integrates facts into climate system strategies. Accesses and uses climate information provided through regional climate service centres (e.g. Pacific Climate Impacts Consortium, Ouranos, etc.) and is able to integrate global and local climate change trends, impacts, challenges and concerns, and use the information to inform policies and practices.	complexity, interaction, different environments trends, impact, challenges, concerns

GreenSCENT – Smart Citizen Education for a Green Future
DL1 – GreenSCENT Competence Framework

3

LINK to the tool:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1yz3oKsv8sbJDEQCtmmJJxtj_hWKu9SO/edit#heading=h.4i7ojhp

Technological tool: GreenSCENT Knowledge Graph

LINK to the tool: https://publish.obsidian.md/greenscent/_START+HERE

3.2.2. Stage B - Planning

Stage B of the GreenSCENT educational framework consists of four steps for academic or professional educators to prepare, organise, and structure the architecture, content, and sequence of the expected learning experience to be provided to their learners.

In this second stage, educators will adopt the GreenSCENT Skills Cards as a practical handbook to select specific learning competencies that match their learners' EQF level, providing an educational experience and learning performance assessment adequate to the target audience's existing competencies.

Consequently, according to the selected competencies, educators can prepare their class orchestration for a particular learning experience.

Using the GreenSCENT tools enables educators to manage this stage properly by providing use-case resources of existing learning programs in sustainability education that can be adopted as ready-to-use formats.

Step B.1: Select the competencies learners need to acquire

B.1.1: Using the GreenSCENT Skill Cards, translate the selected competencies into their corresponding knowledge, skills and attitudes to choose only those compatible with the learners' EQF level.

Tool: GreenSCENT Skill Cards

Nr.	Topic	Skill	Knowledge/Skill	EQF	Statement
1.2.	Climate Change	Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy	Knowledge	1	Understands that climate change is inevitable and that the adaptation is needed to be able to preserve functioning economy without harming nature
1.2.	Climate Change	Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy	Knowledge	2	Knows the consequences of clearing forests, the increase of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, nuclear waste and use of genetically modified organisms
1.2.	Climate Change	Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy	Skills	2	Is able to personally contribute to the energy, water savings as well as reduce air pollution, extinction of plants and animals, by preserving local biodiversity
1.3.	Climate Change	Know-how problem solving	Knowledge	1	Knows that action for climate change need clear identification of a problem and well-defined plan
1.3.	Climate Change	Know-how problem solving	Skills	1	Is able to identify existing issues in the context of climate change
2.1.	Climate Change	Climate Change cross-cultural practice	Knowledge	1	Knows that environmental concerns are not equally distributed across cultures
2.1.	Climate Change	Climate Change cross-cultural practice	Knowledge	2	Is aware that many societies prefer economic and political stability over environmental security
2.1.	Climate Change	Climate Change cross-cultural practice	Skills	1	Identifies what observed impacts of climate change may vary regionally and seasonally
2.2.	Climate Change	Collaboration among diverse stakeholders	Knowledge	1	Knows the existence of many parties that shares the same values for climate change, but also might have diverse interests
2.3.	Climate Change	Climate informed change management	Knowledge	1	Has basic knowledge about the climate change historically and nowadays
2.3.	Climate Change	Climate informed change management	Skills	1	Identifies the features of climate change nowadays
3.1.	Climate Change	Climate change communication	Knowledge	1	Knows different communication channels for climate change

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OK1 - SCENT Skill Cards 26

LINK to the documents: https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/10On8XuxP9vy-JcsgVYtTxyLMNI4_y9CB

Step B.2: Predetermine learning assessment parameters

B.2.1: As for the previous step, translate the selected competencies into their corresponding learning assessment parameters, choosing only those compatible with the learners' EQF level.

Tool: GreenSCENT Skill Cards

3.2.1.1. Skill card – Climate Change – Kids up to 10 years

Nr.	Topic	Skill	Knowledge/Skill	EQF	Statement
1.2.	Climate Change	Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy	Knowledge	1	Understands that climate change is inevitable and that the adaptation is needed to be able to preserve functioning economy without harming nature
1.2.	Climate Change	Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy	Knowledge	2	Knows the consequences of clearing forests, the increase of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, nuclear waste and use of genetically modified organisms
1.2.	Climate Change	Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy	Skills	2	Is able to personally contribute to the energy, water savings as well as reduce air pollution, extinction of plants and animals, by preserving local biodiversity
1.3.	Climate Change	Know-how problem solving	Knowledge	1	Knows that action for climate change need clear identification of a problem and well defined plan
1.3.	Climate Change	Know-how problem solving	Skills	1	Is able to identify existing issues in the context of climate change
2.1	Climate Change	Climate Changecross-cultural practice	Knowledge	1	Knows that environmental concerns are not equally distributed across cultures
2.1	Climate Change	Climate Changecross-cultural practice	Knowledge	2	Is aware that many societies prefer economic and political stability over environmental security
2.1	Climate Change	Climate Changecross-cultural practice	Skills	1	Identifies what observed impacts of climate change may vary regionally and seasonally
2.2.	Climate Change	Collaboration among diverse stakeholders	Knowledge	1	Knows the existence of many parties that shares the same values for climate change, but also might have diverse interests
2.3.	Climate Change	Climate informed change management	Knowledge	1	Has basic knowledge about the climate change historically and nowadays
2.3.	Climate Change	Climate informed change management	Skills	1	Identifies the features of climate change nowadays
3.1.	Climate Change	Climate change communication	Knowledge	1	Knows different communication channels for climate change

GreenSCENT - Smart Citizen Education for a Green Future
Del 1 - SCENT Skill Cards 20

LINK to the documents: https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/10On8XuxP9vy-JcsgVYtTxyLMNI4_y9CB

Step B.3: Design the class orchestration

B.3.1: Once the learning objectives (regarding selected competencies and related learning assessment parameters) are defined, select one of the two options:

1. Choose one example for the GreenSCENT library
2. Fill in the GreenSCENT Instructional Design Template to design a customised class orchestration

The document is divided into six sections that serve to define and structure the overall class orchestration:

- General Information
- Educational objectives & outcomes
- Learning design details
- Educators' preliminary resources
- Duration
- Evaluation

The file helps educators plan educational activities, technologies and resources according to the peculiarities or necessities of their academic or professional educational environment.

Tool: GreenSCENT Instructional Design Template

General Information	
Academic or professional organisation name	
Country	
Project title	
Educator name (s)	
Description of the learners	<i>Please indicate the characteristics of the students/citizens involved (foreseen number of students participating, age, expected background knowledge)</i>
EQF level	<i>https://europass.europa.eu/en/europass-digital-tools/european-qualifications-framework/national-qualifications-frameworks</i>
Certificates/Credits provided	<i>i.e.: ECTS credits in the case of higher education level courses</i>

Educational objectives & outcomes	
Learning objectives	<p>Please provide specific statements describing what learners are expected to know, understand, or be able to do after completing a learning experience. They should refer to the KSAs selected on the GreenSCENT competence framework.</p> <p>Please provide code (es.: 4.1.1) and statements describing the Competencies / KSAs addressed by the module.</p> <p>(Ex. 1.2. Climate Change: Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy, Knowledge, EQF 1)</p>
Learning outcomes	<p>Please provide specific statements describing what learners are expected to know, understand, or be able to do after completing a learning experience. They should refer to the KSAs selected on the Skill Cards.</p> <p>Please provide code (es.: 4.1.1) and statements describing the Competencies / KSAs addressed by the module.</p> <p>(Ex. 1.2. Understands that climate change is inevitable and that adaptation is needed to be able to preserve a functioning economy without harming nature)</p>

Learning design details	
Pre-requisites	Please indicate any prior knowledge and/or skill(s) required to participate in the course/activity
Learning Challenge	<p>Make visible the invisible: Technology aims to raise people's awareness of sustainability by showing the complexity of invisible or imperceptible phenomena to humans' senses. Many techniques and approaches can be used to make more effective use of technology in education, helping people understand problems, make decisions, make predictions, measure and assess the impact of particular actions, and so on.</p> <p>Please describe what strategy you will adopt to make visible some invisible phenomena (ex., anticipation of actions like simulation, prediction, comparison, clear explanation like first-person narration)</p>
Learning methodologies	Please describe the main learning methodologies/approaches used in the module/course. These include experiential, problem-based, project-based, and inquiry-based learning.
Delivery format	Online, hybrid/blended, in-classroom, outside the classroom If online, the amount of synchronous/asynchronous activities
Technologies used in the learning experience	<p>Please describe the technologies (digital or analogue) used in the course/module/experience. Please provide:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Name and a short description of the technology/ies (if one of the GreenSCENT demonstrators, please use standard names/descriptions) - The primary purpose of the technology/ies in the course (collaboration, project work, data collection/processing)

Educators' preliminary resources	
Technology	Please describe what software, hardware and/or interactive devices you need to conduct the course. These could include laptops, smartphones, word-processing software, email services
Time	Please indicate how much time you will need and how you will spend preparing the course material and activities (including pre- and post-activities).
Location	Please specify what kind of space (indoor, outdoor, or both) is required for the course.
Human resources	Please describe the specific skills, knowledge and abilities required to sustain the course.

	<i>How many people are needed to carry out this activity, and describe their role?</i>
Engagement strategies	<i>What strategies will you use to keep participants motivated and actively involved in this activity?</i>
Prior Knowledge	<i>Please indicate what habits, practices, and awareness of concepts the participant must have before conducting the course.</i>
Technical requirements	<i>Please describe what specific technological resources you need to deliver this activity. For example, the availability of electricity, bandwidth, systems, etc.</i>

Duration	
Duration of the course/module	<i>Please express the duration in weeks</i>
Course structure and scheduling	<i>Implementation and scheduling options - fixed duration, part-time, flexibility - average completion duration). Summary of the proposed structure and activities week after week</i>

Evaluation	
Assessment methodology	<i>Please provide a summary of the foreseen assessment methodology, both ongoing and final, if expected: Modality of testing: oral exam, open questions, skill application, portfolio, etc. Nature: online/offline Supervision: supervised/unsupervised</i>

LINK to the document: https://docs.google.com/document/d/17NHreIXUk7Z-5QGzb2QjifRra_rTOiZ2a/edit

Step B.4: Define the learning experience

B.4.1: According to the information described in the GreenSCENT_Instruction Design template, select one of the two options:

1. Choose one Use Case example for the GreenSCENT library
2. Fill in the GreenSCENT Use Case Template accordingly

The Use Case to define a unique learning experience tailored to the interests and needs of the academic or professional educational environment.

The document includes three main sections:

- Description of the learning objectives and skills cards selected during stage B - planning
- Description of the learning activity description defined in stage C - execution
- Description of the learning assessment parameters selected during stage B - planning

Instructional Design Model

The learning activity follows the GreenSCENT model, which divides the educational experience into three main steps:

- Assignment
- Challenge
- Documentary/Report

These lead the learners to analyse a particular challenge in sustainability education, investigate it through a practical on-field exploration and research, and then document it by developing a documentary or a report as a tangible result and artefact of the proposed learning experience.

B.4.2: In the first step, provide learners with educational material (such as a scientific paper) to study a particular challenge in sustainability and gain new knowledge before the practical activity.

The assignment must be delivered to learners a few days before the launch of the practical activity, allowing them to adequately assess their competence in tackling the environmental challenge.

B.4.3: In the second activity, define all the steps of practical and on-field research with the learners. The experience involves exploring the challenge by adopting one of the GreenSCENT technologies, which are:

- GreenSCENT Environmental Monitoring App
- GreenSCENT Citizen Journalism
- GreenSCENT Air Quality App
- GreenSCENT CleanAir@School

The GreenSCENT material provides educators with specific user manuals that explain the correct use of each GreenSCENT technology. They help educators organise and structure the educational experience based on their purposes and technical properties.

The GreenSCENT technology selection depends on the learning objectives selected in Stage B - Planning and the learners' EQF level.

B.4.4: In the third activity, define the outcome the learners must achieve and produce regarding analogical or digital documentaries/reports that provide information (in the form of storytelling) about how they understood the environmental challenge and faced during the previous steps.

According to the learning objectives selected in Stage B - Planning and the learners' EQF level, the documentary/report can be produced physically or virtually with analogue or digital tools such as an essay, poster, PowerPoint presentation, or static or immersive storyboards using:

- the GreenSCENT 360° paper-based template
- the GreenVerse 360 Interactive Documentary

The GreenSCENT material provides educators with specific user manuals that explain the correct use of each GreenSCENT technology. They help educators organise and structure the educational experience based on their purposes and technical properties.

Tool: GreenSCENT Use Case Template

	<p><i>competence framework and listed in the GreenSCENT Instructional Design Template)</i></p> <p>Knowledge:</p> <p>Skill:</p> <p>Attitude:</p>	
<p>ASSIGNMENT</p> <p>Article: <i>(ex. Read an article about the recycling policies of your local authority and provide a summary)</i></p>	<p>CHALLENGE</p> <p>Challenge title description:</p> <p>Practical activity steps:</p> <p>Tool: <i>(GreenSCENT technology or other analogic tools)</i></p>	<p>DOCUMENTARY/REPORT</p> <p>Documentary title description:</p> <p>Guidelines for developing the documentary:</p> <p>Interaction:</p> <p>Expected output:</p> <p>Tool: <i>(GreenVerse 360 Interactive Documentary, Paper-based 360 Interactive Documentary Template or other analogic tools)</i></p>
<p>LEARNING ASSESSMENT</p> <p><i>(Please provide code (es.: 4.1.1) and statements describing the selected GreenSCENT statements the learning experience addresses.</i></p> <p><i>They should refer to the KSAs selected on the GreenSCENT Skil Cards and listed in the GreenSCENT Instructional Design Template)</i></p>		

LINK to the tool:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1xSSZaEJega9yPz5fY_YymhvPIBSVL1zKsmWt7HMYeyl/edit?tab=t.0

Technological tool: User Manual - GreenSCENT Environmental Monitoring App

LINK to the document: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/18x3-gMejDadA3MpQkuJMAh45otQDGUzd>

Technological tool: User Manual - GreenSCENT Citizen Journalism

LINK to the document: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1eR8HpKKcQbt3QsDjcmQMligmxk1ZZZl>

Technological tool: User Manual - GreenSCENT Air Quality App

LINK to the document: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1GX0uTipEeJV7yhb_2z9rdi8g6XSXw1NG

Technological tool: User Manual - GreenSCENT CleanAir@School

LINK to the document: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1MbK6tEXywuP6MDQT4niInVIX8XFUJKgn>

Technological tool: User Manual - GreenSCENT GreenVerse Interactive documentary

LINK to the document: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1uba6H8tCwACmEUe8nB0odCcTqiD4uv4B>

Technological tool: User Manual - GreenSCENT 360° paper-based template

LINK to the document: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1uba6H8tCwACmEUe8nB0odCcTqiD4uv4B>

Tool: User Manual - GreenSCENT GreenVerse Interactive documentary

LINK to the document:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1OcHxWwTOq6Vm-h1q1HvFuuf77An46HKR>

3.2.3. Stage C - Execution

Stage C of the GreenSCENT educational framework consists of running the learning experience in sustainability education involving learners directly in theoretical but primarily practical activities that help them acquire new environmental awareness and pro-environmental competencies according to the learning objectives and outcomes defined in the previous stages.

The third phase represents five main steps to evaluate the learners' learning performance during the educational experience. The first and last phases concern measuring and evaluating the learners' learning performance before and after the practical activities.

The three intermediate phases must adhere to the same learning activities described in the educator's selected Use Case (Step B.4.1) to allow learners to perform activities and develop competence in sustainability education according to the learning process (targeted needs, objectives and outcomes) defined in Stage B - Planning.

Step C.1: Administrate the impact assessment on pro-environmental behaviours ex-ante

C.1.1: Administrate the GreenSCENT Competence Questionnaire to each learner before conducting the educational activities.

The tool measures automatic biases and attitudes toward environmental actions and themes by using the Brief Implicit Association Test (BIAT), a streamlined version of the Implicit Association Test.

The questionnaire should be administered in person if necessary to guide learners. Completing it takes approximately 20-30 minutes without interruption.

This procedure requires each learner to have a computer to install the Inquisit software and an associated plugin to conduct the test. The learning program must be represented by a specific ID code that can be used to identify the results obtained in that particular educational experience. The exact ID must be recorded to be used again at the end of the learning activity.

The software installation and the procedure description are described in the specific instructions of the questionnaire.

Tool: GreenSCENT Competence Questionnaire ex-ante

LINK to the tool: <https://mili2nd.eu/z6ec>

Step C.2: Provide the assignment

C.2.1: Assign learners the study and investigation of a particular challenge in sustainability – that addresses the learning objectives defined in Stage B - Planning – by providing them with educational material (such as a scientific paper) that supports gaining new knowledge and competencies before the practical activity.

The learners' investigation can be supported by adopting the GreenSCENT Knowledge Graph.

The assignment's typology and goal of this step are explicitly declared in the assignment section of the GreenSCENT Use Case. The task must be delivered to learners a few days before the launch of the practical activity, allowing them to assess their competence in tackling the environmental challenge.

C.3.3: Monitor learners' progress and help them follow every step correctly till they conclude the activity.

Step C.3: Launch the challenge

C.3.1: Deliver the instruction of the learning challenge according to the planned design and steps described in the selected GreenSCENT Use Case.

C.3.2: Provide learners with the select tools and GreenSCENT technologies and teach them how to use them to achieve the objectives of the learning challenge. Using user manuals and a short demo can better explain the correct use of a given GreenSCENT technology.

C.3.3: Monitor learners' progress during the on-field research by asking them to collect specific environmental information or practical activities and helping them follow every step correctly until they conclude the process.

Step C.4: Require documentation for evaluation

C.4.1: Deliver instruction on organising learners' note-taking and brainstorm several ideas to structure the storytelling for the final documentary or report, as described in the documentary/report section of the selected GreenSCENT Use Case.

C.4.2: Provide learners with specific analogic tools or the GreeVerse 360 Immersive Platform and teach them how to use them to develop their storytelling and documentation of a sustainability-related phenomenon. User manuals and a short demo can better explain how to use a given analogical tool or technology correctly.

C.3.3: Monitor learners' progress during the development phase by asking them to generate a specific analogue or digital artefact and help them follow every step correctly until they conclude the documenting process.

C.4.4: Ask learners to give a short plenary presentation of the achieved results, sharing and criticising the final learning outcome in an open discussion with all the participants.

Step C.5: Administrate the impact assessment on pro-environmental behaviours ex-post

C.5.1: Administrate the GreenSCENT Competence Questionnaire to each learner after conducting the educational activities.

The questionnaire should be administered in person if necessary to guide learners. Completing it takes approximately 20-30 minutes without interruption.

This procedure follows the ex-ante administration, so each learner must have the Inquisit software and an associated plugin installed to conduct the test. The learners must adopt the same ID used in the first assessment (Step C.1.1) to identify the results of their learning performance from the same educational experience.

The software installation and the procedure description are described in the specific instructions of the questionnaire.

Tool: GreenSCENT Competence Questionnaire ex-post

LINK to the tool: <https://mili2nd.eu/z6ec>

3.2.4. Stage D - Evaluation

Stage D of the GreenSCENT educational framework evaluates the learners' learning performance in sustainability education acquired during the educational experience.

Educators must analyse the activities and the learning outcomes to assess the learners' new environmental awareness and pro-environmental competencies based on a specific Green Deal area declared in the Use Case.

The fourth and last phase represents one main task, which measures and evaluates each learner's learning performance after the practical activities through a specific document that enables educators to assess according to the learning objectives and outcomes defined and developed in the previous stages.

Step D.1: Evaluate learning performance

D.1.1: Using the GreenSCENT Learning Performance Assessment template, evaluate the learners' learning performance according to the learning assessment parameters selected in stage B - Planning.

The template is composed of two pages:

- Page 1 - Description of the educational experience that must be evaluated
- Page 2 - Assessment Rubric for evaluation of learners' performance

The first page includes three main sections:

- Description of the learning objectives and skills cards selected during stage B - planning
- Description of the learning activity description defined in stage C - execution
- Representation of the results documented by the learners' work during step C.4 of the execution stage

The second page includes the assessment rubric with the details of the learning assessment criteria:

- **LC0 - Group Engagement:** Group members' active contribution to the activity
- **LC1 - Motivation:** Active contribution to the activity
- **LC2 - Novelty:** Novelty of scope and role of the artefact
- **LC3 - Accuracy:** Record evidence appropriate to Objectives and Skills
- **LC4 - Elaboration:** Explore data to develop informed connections
- **LC5 - Presentation:** Efficacy of communication

For each criterion, three levels have been proposed based on the EQF level of the learning experience:

- Level 1 - Basic
- Level 2 - Intermediate
- Level 3 - Advanced

The evaluation is provided by checking the appropriate score for each criterion.

Step D.2: Officialise assessment for ECQA certification

D.2.1: Provide the learners' learning performance assessment to the ECQA system to receive a pre-certification based on the competencies selected in stage B - Planning.

This can be conducted by signing each learner's Learning Performance Assessment document to officially mark the completion of the educational activities on sustainability education.

Tool: GreenSCENT Learning Performance Assessment Template

LEARNING PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT	
Description - Page 1	
Teacher / Educator: [Name] - [Surname]	
Education Level: [Educational level]	Education Grade: [Grade]
Pilot ID Number: [ID number]	Institution: [Institution name]
Country: [Country]	GreenSCENT Demonstrator/s: [Demonstrator/s name]
Name of the learner or team group: [learner's name and surname] or [Team's name]	
Team group's number of members: [Number of members]	
<p>SKILL CARDS</p> <p>Green Deal Domain / Objective: <i>Please provide code (es.: 4.1.1) and statements describing the selected Green Deal area and competencies the learning experience addresses. They should refer to the Knowledge Skills and Attitudes (KSA) in the GreenSCENT competence framework.</i></p> <p>Knowledge: <i>Please provide code (es.: 4.1.1) and statements of the skill cards that describe the knowledge addressed by the selected competencies.</i></p> <p>Skills: <i>Please provide code (es.: 4.1.1) and statements of the skill cards that describe the skills addressed by the selected competencies.</i></p> <p>Attitudes: <i>Please provide code (es.: 4.1.1) and statements of the skill cards that describe the attitudes addressed by the selected competencies.</i></p>	<p>EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITY</p> <p>Challenge: <i>Please describe the selected educational challenge proposed by the learning experience.</i></p> <p>Exploration: <i>Please describe the activity/activities of the learning experience.</i></p>
TANGIBLE RESULTS <i>Please insert here the tangible results the learner or group of learners accomplished during the learning experience. This could be a link to the project, image, video, graphics or attachment.</i>	

LEARNING PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT Assessment Rubric - Page 2			
<i>Please mark every criterion with an "X" according to the level achieved by the learner or group of learners.</i>			
<i>Criteria</i>	<i>1 Basic</i>	<i>2 Intermediate</i>	<i>3 Advanced</i>
LC0 Group Engagement: Group members' active contribution to the activity.	Share(s) ideas but do not advance the group's work.	Offer(s) new suggestions to advance the work of the group.	Help(s) the team move forward by articulating the merits of alternative ideas or proposals.
LC1 Motivation: Active contribution to the activity.	Motivated only when the external controller is present	Coherently motivated to accomplish the workgroup objectives.	Intrinsically motivated to view collaboration as a journey driven by a shared purpose that is aligned with their core values
LC2 Novelty Novelty or uniqueness (of idea, claim, question, form, final result.	Reformulates a collection of available ideas.	Iteratively develops novel ideas, questions, formats, or products.	Breaks new ground by building on a novel concept to generate entirely new knowledge or transdisciplinary understanding.
LC3 Accuracy Record evidence appropriate to Objectives and Skills	Lists evidence, but it needs to be organised and/or is unrelated to focus.	Organise evidence in a structured format; however, the current organisation may need to fully highlight key patterns, differences, or similarities.	Organises and synthesises evidence to reveal insightful patterns, differences, or similarities related to focus.
LC4 Elaboration Explore data to develop informed connections	Information is taken from source(s) without any interpretation/evaluation. Expert viewpoints are taken as fact, without question.	Information is taken from source(s) with some interpretation/evaluation, but more is needed to develop a coherent analysis or synthesis. Expert viewpoints are taken as main facts, with little questioning.	Information is taken from source(s) with enough interpretation/evaluation to develop a comprehensive analysis or synthesis. Expert viewpoints are questioned thoroughly.
LC5 Presentation Efficacy of communication	The presentation is generally clear but could benefit from repetition and stronger emphasis for better retention. The speaker(s)'s delivery could be more confident, and the overall	The presentation is clear and consistent. Speaker(s) appears comfortable. While the structure of the presentation could have been clearer, there were some organised elements.	The speaker(s) delivered a polished and confident presentation. The presentation was compelling. Skilled organisation ensures a cohesive flow of content,

	structure of the presentation could be improved for better clarity.		making the presentation easy to follow.

(If available) DEMONSTRATOR-SPECIFIC LEARNING ASSESSMENT

Please describe any specific additional competence the learner or group of learners has/have acquired during the learning experience by using the selected GreenSCENT demonstrator.

LINK to the document:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/17myfVQziFOR8MaliG_envetoYrZMotLYEaHaO9XzJBc/edit?tab=t.0

4. User Guide: European certification

4.1. Evaluation and Certification Methodology

After the practical activities, educators can certify each learner's learning performance according to their educational level through a European certification, which can be requested through the European Certification for Climate and Environmental Literacy (ECCEL) certificate, delivered by ECQA GmbH.

4.1.1. Properties of the evaluation process

ECQA GmbH is using a significantly up-to-date exam portal. Within this portal, certification exams and self-assessments can be made. The primary difference is that self-assessments are free of charge (demo exams), while exams are typically paid for (business case).

Individuals certified under this certification scheme are competent to independently plan and deliver ECCEL as a service, using appropriate technical tools and applications to evaluate learning performance in three different levels of competencies:

- Beginners
- Advanced
- Professional

The typical exam types the advisory board must choose from are multiple-choice and multiple-response. However, the exam portal can also facilitate using other exam question types, as seen below:

- Multiple Choice
- Multiple Response
- Drag and Drop
- Essay (Free text with editor)
- Fill in / Select Blanks
- Hotspot
- Knowledge Matrix
- Likert Scale
- Atching (also Drag&Drop Matching)
- Numeric
- Multiple lists (Pulldown, MC)
- Spreadsheet
- Coding
- Ranking
- Survey Matrix
- Text Match
- True/False
- Yes/No
- Interacting Image / Screen Simulator
- Sortable (through Drag & Drop)
- Content Only
- MS Excel (only with Windows lockdown client)
- File Upload
- Photo-based answer

Within a skill card, typically, the complete skill card is separated into Units and Elements. The advisory board and all the partners will decide on a threshold within the exams per unit/element needed to pass the exam.

Possible solutions are:

- Passing per skill card: Candidates who take an examination typically need to answer a certain number of questions (as agreed by the advisory board) for all topics within a skill card. A certain number of these questions need to be answered correctly to pass the exam. If the exam fails, candidates must retake the complete exam.
- Passing per unit: Candidates who take an examination typically need to answer a certain number of questions (as agreed by the advisory board) per unit within the skill card to pass the exam. To pass the exam, a certain number of questions of every (!) unit need to be answered correctly. If the exam fails, candidates must retake the not-passed units.
- Passing per element: The units that have already passed will not be shown again. Here, micro certificates per passed unit may be issued rather than the typical certificate for a completed skill card.

4.1.2. European Certificate

Possible certificates will include the candidate's Last name and First name, an individual number (exam portal), the date of the exam, the date until the certificate is valid, and the name of the skill card or, in the case of micro certificates, the name of the passed unit.

Typically, all units and elements (sometimes even learning objectives and EQF levels) and all the agreed-upon partner logos will be visible on the second page. A space will be in the lower left corner, where the digital validation of the PDF file will be located.

These certificates will be prepared to use the new European digital credential system, making it easy to include these skills and competencies and even complete certificates in platforms like Europass or LinkedIn.

Tool: European Certification for Climate and Environmental Literacy (ECCEL)

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